

HATE SPEECH DETECTION USING MACHINE LEARNING

Abhishek Sharma
 Department of CSE,
 ASET
 Amity University,
 Noida, India
abhisheksharma1612200@gmail.com

Khush Sharma
 Department of CSE,
 ASET
 Amity University,
 Noida, India
whyiamkhush@gmail.com

Shyamal Bajaj
 Department of CSE,
 ASET,
 Amity University,
 Noida, India
Shaymalbajaj1999@gmail.com

Dr. Neha Agarwal
 Department of CSE,
 ASET
 Amity University,
 Noida,India
agarwalnehajain@gmail.com

Abstract - The evolvement of the Internet and social websites gave society multiple platforms where everyone has free rein to disseminate their ideas. However, this liberty is being abused by some to spread hate speech texts on these networking forums against particular individuals or circles of people due to their ethnicity, faith, gender, etc. In recent years, these hate speech texts could be perceived as the seeds for cyberbullying cases and major conflicts all across social media forums. Thus, to solve this concern of hate speech texts recent studies incorporated a majority of feature engineering approaches and machine learning models to automate this process of detecting hate speech in messages on various datasets. Hence, this paper aims to collate comparisons between numerous machine learning models and train a machine learning model using publicly available datasets giving the best accuracy and being the most capable model for detecting hate speech. This paper talks about the classification of audio data extracted from Videos that can be classified as either normal or offensive based on their spoken content. To create the video dataset, a web scraping program called Crawler is used to identify videos containing specific types of offensive content. After that audio is extracted from the video using a speech-to-text converter and converted into textual data. After that, we use this textual data and work with other machine learning algorithms.

Keywords - Hate speech, machine learning, deep learning.

1.INTRODUCTION

In the year 2023, the world population crossed the 8 billion lives milestone and as of data recorded in the year 2022, 4.8 billion people of this count are exposed to social media networking websites [1]. Hence, Social media users will consistently increase and data analysts also claim that broadly in a year 150 million new users are joining social forums [2]. The boundaries to communicate across the world are contracting and everyone is more connected than they ever were but with positives comes negatives too. The negative in this case is hate speech.

Hate speech has been more prevalent both offline and online in the past few years. The right to express oneself freely belongs to everyone. The freedom of expression is being abused to injure others and engage in verbal or physical discrimination. This bigotry can be conceivable as hate speech [3]. Speaking out against someone or a group of people because of their tribe, culture, faith, ethnicity, gender-specific, nation, sexual orientation, or other qualities is known as hate speech. It can be communicated vocally, through scripted, tangible signs, or displays that criticize others for being members of a particular social group.

Figure 1 Hierarchy of hate speech content [4]

It takes a lot of valuable time and manpower to identify and eliminate hate speech data. Because of these problems and the ubiquity of hate speech content on these social platforms, there is a strong push for automatic hate speech identification. Due to conflicts over various definitions of hate speech, automatic identification of hate speech is a rigorous task. Consequently, depending on their respective definitions and perceptions, some people may find certain content to be offensive while others may not.

As we all know that we can't eliminate hate speech fully but we can work on finding it and removing it as much as we can and spreading awareness about how to become aware if anyone is expressing hate

comments or offensive comments. So, to find hate speech we made this project in which first we are going to find the accuracy of different models like Naive Bayes [5], SVM [6], Random Forest, and recurrent neural network (RNN). And find out which model gives the best accuracy in finding hate speech using feature extraction methods like tokenization (in which we usually break down complex sentences to simple words), and stemming (in which we reduce a word to its root form), removing of stop words (that doesn't affect the meaning of the whole sentence) and other different techniques.

But as we all know; it is easy to do so because there are so many sources out there through which we can do that but we also worked on converting speech data to textual data to detect hate speech from a simple video by using different speech to text methods to find our result. And finding out if our model is able to predict whether our speech file has hate speech or not.

This paper is organized as follows: As we acknowledge that our expertise on this subject is inadequate, we will give a quick summary of pertinent research on hate speech in the introduction section. Secondly, we are going to go to methodology where we will talk about the approach we used. Thirdly, we are going to discuss our approach and finally we present the result and conclusion of the paper.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

Over many years, different solutions have been proposed for detecting hate speech problem using different approaches like machine learning, natural language processing and deep learning. In [7] author used Natural Language Processing (NLP) method to detect hate speech in tweets and he used Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) method to identify tweets as hate, offensive and no hate. And using that technique author get 91% accuracy in the result. In [8] author implemented different approaches like Naive Bayes, Linear SVM, Random Forest techniques to detect the hate speech in videos which usually deals with changing video into text using different APIs and other speech-to-text methods, but author get the accuracy of 96% using Random Forest Classifier.

In [9] researchers work on a machine learning technique to find out hate speech in tweet data. First, they simply made vectors using vectorizer techniques and applied different machine learning approaches. But Random Forest technique gives the highest accuracy in terms of F1 score and accuracy of model. In [10] author inspected hate speech Detection in Hindi English tweets. He used 3 different deep learning techniques to find the effectiveness of the methods. And it shows that these

deep learning techniques gives for accurate textual data.

3.METHODOLOGY

The project aims to classify the video into two categories, i.e.one being toxic speech (hate/abusive speech) and other one non-abusive speech (normal speech) on basis of the audio present in the video. The working design of the program is explained in the flowchart below.

Figure 2 process of converting into text[11]

- a. Get video from YouTube using URL.
- b. Extract audio data from video.
- c. Transform Audio to Text.
- d. Using the Text-Features train ML model to analyze the video as toxic or normal.

A. Dataset

Upon searching the various open dataset platforms, we found out there were no usable datasets for detecting hate speech from audios. So, the first step was to manually label the videos as hateful and non-hateful. There are many ways in which hate speech can be categorized, we only focused upon the sexist and racist ones in this project.

To build a dataset, we would need to fetch YouTube videos using a crawler. "YouTube API" provides features to search videos based upon keyword but to download the video we would require another library "PyTube" with downloads videos based on URL provided.

To store the large amounts of videos to further train our model we would also require a cloud space.

Videos	Category
https://youtu.be/CA2h5a5004	Normal
https://youtu.be/x9RIW-OrmY	Racist
https://youtu.be/Ug144Y05qw	Sexist

Table 1 Classification of Videos

B. Processing of Videos

To process the data, we will be using a well-liked open-source multimedia framework – “FFmpeg” which has the ability to demultiplex, encrypt, transcode, multiplex, decrypt, stream, and filter audio and video files in a variety of formats. Developers may interact with the framework and create software that processes multimedia files using the robust set of APIs that FFmpeg offers.

Few of the most popular FFmpeg APIs would be the following :

- i. *libavcodec*: This API offers capability for encoding and decoding for several audio and video codecs. It has compatibility for several different codecs, including H.264, MPEG-4, AAC, MP3, and numerous more. Other FFmpeg libraries employ a variety of utility functions. It has functions for handling memory, arithmetic, data structures, and other things.
- ii. *libswscale*: This API offers capabilities for scaling and converting images. It enables programmers to resize photos and change their colour spaces and file formats.
- iii. *libavfilter*: This API offers a foundation for applying filters to audio and video data. It has a large selection of filters for many different purposes, including scaling, colour correction, noise reduction, and more.
- iv. *libavdevice*: This API enables the recording of audio and video from a variety of input devices, including capture cards, microphones, and webcams.
- v. Overall, the FFmpeg APIs give programmers a complete set of tools for working with multimedia files and carrying out a variety of activities connected to processing audio and video.

The next step involves converting the audio to text data.

Programmers can convert oral data into written data format using the Cloud Speech-to-Text API, the assistance provided by Google Cloud. This API detects speech patterns and precisely transforms them into textual data using state of an art machine-learning algorithms.

Programmers can consider audio recordings of any size, in any programming language, and at any scale using the Cloud Speech-to-Text API. The API

also authorizes live broadcasting, providing programmers to record vocal content while it is being said.

As stated earlier, after getting the required video in audio format its uploaded to google bucket. The textual data is stored in a document for further training the model.

C. Categorization Of Dataset

To label the dataset into three categories we apply the sentiment analysis on the given dataset using NLP.

To perform this we would require a python library: ‘TextBlob’, which is constructed with base constituent as (NLTK) Natural Language Toolkit library, which cater a suite of tools and resources for natural language processing in Python. ‘TextBlob’ provides a higher-level API for common NLP tasks, making it easier to use and more accessible for beginners. TextBlob uses a machine learning algorithm to calculate the sentiment polarity and subjectivity of a text. The algorithm is trained on a corpus of movie reviews and uses a Naive Bayes classifier to classify the text as positive or negative based on the presence of certain words and phrases. The sentiment polarity ranges from -1 (negative) to 1 (positive), and the subjectivity ranges from 0 (objective) to 1 (subjective).

After finding out the Sentiment polarity of each sentence and deciding if this categorization was enough and correct, however it was not fully correct which would lead to a lower accuracy result.

D. Feature Engineering

Now, we have data in text format after getting processed by multiple API’s. Google Cloud Speech-to-text API needs to remove stop word to process data, but in addition to that we would also need to process it since it is now in text format.

The two features we would require to implement would be :

- i. *CountVectorization*:

CountVectorizer is a technique in natural language processing (NLP) that is used to convert a collection of text documents into a matrix of token counts. It is a type of feature extraction that is commonly used in machine learning models for text classification, sentiment analysis, topic modelling, and other NLP tasks. The basic idea behind CountVectorizer is to represent each document in the corpus as a vector of word counts. The rows of the resulting matrix represent the documents, while the columns represent the words in the corpus. Each cell in the matrix represents the frequency of a

particular word in a particular document. The CountVectorizer algorithm works as follows:

- **Tokenization:** The first step is to split each document into its constituent words, or tokens. This can be done using a simple whitespace tokenizer, or more sophisticated tokenization techniques such as regular expressions or NLTK.
- **Vocabulary Building:** The next step is to create a vocabulary of all the unique words in the corpus. This is done by assigning a unique integer to each word in the corpus and creating a dictionary that maps each word to its integer.
- **Vectorization:** Once the vocabulary is created, each document can be represented as a word count's vector. The vector length is equivalent to the vocabulary's size, and the value of every single element in the vector is the count of the co-relative word in the document.
- **Normalization:** Optionally, the resulting vectors can be normalized to account for differences in document length and to prevent common words from dominating the analysis.

ii. *TfidfVectorization:*

F-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) is a numerical statistic that reflects the importance of a word in a document corpus. In natural language processing (NLP), the TF-IDF statistic is often used as a weighting factor in text analysis and information retrieval. TF-IDF Vectorization is a technique used in machine learning to convert a collection of text documents into a numerical matrix's feature, where each tuple represents a document and each domain represents a term, with each element representing the TF-IDF score for a given term in a given document.

Using the above two processing, we get text in N-gram encoded format. N-grams are commonly used in NLP for a variety of tasks, including language modelling, text classification, and machine translation. By capturing the context and relationships between adjacent words in a sequence, n-grams can help to improve the accuracy of machine learning models by providing more detailed information about the structure and meaning of text data.

The processed data helps in determination of features best useful for classification of text into the desired categories.

E. *Machine Learning Model*

We have used many models to find out the different accuracy and performance results which are shared later on in the paper.

- i. **Naive Bayes** A probabilistic technique called Naive Bayes employs the Bayes theorem to categorise data. It is an easy-to-use, quick method that handles large datasets amiably. The general stages for training a Naive Bayes model are as follows:
 - a. Coding category variables and scaling numerical variables will prepare the content.
 - b. Generate testing and training sets from the content.
 - c. According to Naive Bayes model the content is trained.
 - d. Analyse the model's performance using the test data.
- ii. **Linear SVM** A well-liked algorithm for binary classification issues is linear SVM. It functions by identifying the hyperplane having the greatest margin of separation between the classes. The general stages for training a Linear SVM model are as follows:
 - a. Coding category variables and scaling numerical variables will prepare the content.
 - b. Create training and test sets from the data.
 - c. According to SVM model the content is trained.
 - d. Using cross-validation on the training data, adjust the hyperparameters.
 - e. Analyse the model's performance using the test data.
- iii. **Random Forest** A prediction is made using an ensemble technique called Random Forest that mixes different decision trees. It functions by building several decision trees on various random subsets of data and combining the results. The general steps for training a Random Forest model are as follows:
 - a. Coding category variables and scaling numerical variables will prepare the content.
 - b. Generate testing and training sets from the content.
 - c. According to the Random Forest model the content is trained.
 - d. Using cross-validation on the training data, adjust the hyperparameters.

- e. Analyse the model's performance using the test data.
- iv. Recurrent neural networks, or RNNs, are a subset of neural networks that can process time-series data as well as text data. They operate by successively processing the data input and feeding the output of one time step into the next. The general steps for training an RNN model are as follows:
 - a. Transform the data into a series of vectors to prepare it.
 - b. Create training and test sets from the data.
 - c. Create the model and specify the RNN architecture.
 - d. Fit the training data to the RNN model.
 - e. Analyse the model's performance using the test data.

Fig. 3 Two Labels accuracy model

4.RESULT

We classify the textual data as hateful and non-hateful. We have considered all the textual data as non-hateful. After doing all the calculations we marked some data as hateful and others as non-hateful and we use the following parameters to find these results:

F1 score - which usually means the accuracy of a model which considers both recall and precision score.

$$F1 \text{ score} = 2 \times (\text{precision} \times \text{recall}) / (\text{precision} + \text{recall})$$

Recall - Recall is the method to find the true positive of a model.

$$\text{Recall} = TP / (TP + FN)$$

Precision - It is the measure of a model to find the true positive of a model out of all positive of a model.

$$\text{Precision} = TP / (TP + FP)$$

The average of accuracy of all four models are calculated and plotted in the form of bar chart using matplotlib.

Fig. 4 Three Labels accuracy model

Instead of using criteria in the corpus, we classify the tweets as Strongly Hateful, Weakly Hateful, or Not hate. We have considered all the tweets classified as non-hostile by the algorithm as No Hate, All the tweets marked as fake or defamatory are marked as Weakly Hateful, The tweets that are marked hate, Offensive, or a combination of one or more tags correspond to Strongly Hateful. The following parameters are used to evaluate the performance of the classifier.

Receiver Operating Characteristic is referred to as ROC. It is used to implement a visual representation of the performance of a binary classifier system while the discrimination level is changed. The ROC curve is obtained by plotting the true positive rate versus the false positive rate at different starting values. The TPR, also known as sensitivity or recall, is the proportion of true positives to all actual positives. The false positive rate (FPR) is defined as the proportion of false positives to all actual negatives. A ROC curve

passing through the top left corner of the plot, which stands for a TPR of 1 and an FPR of 0, would indicate a perfect classifier. An indicator of the classifier's overall effectiveness is the area under the ROC curve (AUC), with a value of 1 denoting a perfect classifier and a value of 0.5 denoting a classifier that performs no better than random guessing. Our results show that the Random Forrest algorithm produces an area under the curve of value 0.97, whereas the Multinomial Naive Bayes model and Linear SVM algorithm produce an area under the curve of value 1. and an area under a curve of 0.50 is produced using a recurrent neural network model. These findings suggest that the recurrent neural network algorithm is not able to divide our data into the appropriate groups. We must reconsider the danger of overfitting due to the small dataset as our model is producing an ideal AUC of 0.99 and 1.

TABLE 2
AVERAGE RESULTS OF EXPERIMENT 1

	Accuracy	Precision Score	Recall Score	F1 Score
Multinomial Naïve Bayes	0.8512	0.8833	0.8533	0.8267
Linear SVM	0.8929	0.9133	0.8933	0.89
Random Forrest	0.9464	0.95	0.9467	0.9433
RNN	0.8036	0.65	0.80	0.72

TABLE 3
AVERAGE RESULTS OF EXPERIMENT 2

	Accuracy	Precision Score	Recall Score	F1 Score
Multinomial Naïve Bayes	0.7976	0.78	0.7967	0.7567
Linear SVM	0.8214	0.7933	0.8233	0.7967
Random Forrest	0.8571	0.7733	0.86	0.81
RNN	0.8036	0.65	0.80	0.72

5.CONCLUSION

We all executed a technique to find hate speech in YouTube videos which deal with transforming the video content into textual data prior to transferring it as input to machine learning algorithms. We trained and assessed numerous machine learning algorithms to calculate values such as precision ratio, recall, accuracy and f1 to get the best and most effective model for the given data. According to the concluding remarks, the Random Forrest Classifier algorithms produced the most accurate results, achieving a precision rate of 96%.

Our proposed approach can be expanded to classify more than three categories and improve classification accuracy by increasing the dataset size. This study utilized the Google Speech-to-Text API to transcribe spoken content, but other speech-

to-text generators or APIs could also be explored for potential improvements. Additionally, future research could incorporate the speaker's tone to better understand the context of the speech, which could enhance the detection of hate speech.

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